

AQAR

2015-16

PART - I

Chairperson	:	Dr. Vandana Agnihotri Principal
Coordinator	:	Dr. H.K. Garg Professor of Zoology
Asstt. Coordinator	:	Dr. Veena Dani Professor of Psychology
Members	{	Dr. G.P. Yadav Dr. Kiran Sharma Dr. Kusum Mathur

INTERNAL QUALITY ASSURANCE CELL
SAROJINI NAIDU GOVERNMENT GIRLS POST GRADUATE AUTONOMOUS COLLEGE
SHIVAJI NAGAR BHOPAL

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Internal Quality Assurance Cell

The Annual Quality Assurance Report (AQAR) of the IQAC

All NAAC accredited institutions will submit an annual self-reviewed progress report to NAAC, through its IQAC. The report is to detail the tangible results achieved in key areas, specifically identified by the institutional IQAC at the beginning of the academic year. The AQAR will detail the results of the perspective plan worked out by the IQAC.

(Note: The AQAR period would be the Academic Year. For example, July 1, 2012 to June 30, 2013)

Part - A

1. Details of the Institution

1.	Name of the Institution	Sarojini Naidu Govt. Girls Post Graduate (Autonomous) College
2.	Address Line	Shivaji Nagar
3.	City/Town	Bhopal
4.	State	Madhya Pradesh
5.	Pin Code	462016
6.	Institution email	hegsngpgcbho@mp.gov.in
7.	Contact Nos.	0755 - 2552560
8.	Name of the Head of the Institution	Dr.Vandana Agnihotri
9.	Tel. No. with STD Code:	0755 - 2469466
10.	Mobile	+91 - 9893280908
11.	Name of the IQAC Coordinator	Dr. H.K. GARG
12.	Mobile	09424417792
13.	IQAC e-mail address	iqacsngpgcbpl@gmail.com
14.	NAAC Track ID (For ex. MHCOGN 18879)	MPCOGN - 10173
15.	NAAC Executive Committee No. & Date:(For Example EC/32/A&A/ 143 dated 3-5-2004. This EC no. is available in the right corner- bottom of your institution's Accreditation Certificate)	EC/PCRAR/49/01 Dated June 15 th , 2009
16.	Website address	www.snpcollege.in
17.	Web-link of the AQAR	http://www.snpcollege.in/IQAC

For ex. <http://www.ladykeanecollege.edu.in/AQAR2012-13.doc>

Accreditation Details					
S. No.	Cycle	Grade	CGPA	Year of Accreditation	Validity Period
1.	1 st Cycle	B	75%	15.05.2002	5 years
2.	2 nd Cycle	B	2.88	15.06.2009	5 years
3.	3 rd Cycle	Due			
4.	4 th Cycle				
19.	Date of Establishment of IQAC	DD/MM/YYYY		10/01/2003	
20.	AQAR for the year (for example 2010-11)			2015 - 2016	
21.	Details of the previous year's AQAR submitted to NAAC after the latest Assessment and Accreditation by NAAC (for example AQAR 2010-11 submitted to NAAC on 12-10-2011)				
22.	AQAR 2012-13 submitted to NAAC			22-09-2013	
23.	AQAR 2013-14 submitted to NAAC			30-06-2014	
24.	AQAR 2014-15 submitted to NAAC			23-09-2015	
25.	Institutional Status				
	University	State		-	-
	Affiliated College	Yes		√	No
	Constituent College	Yes		-	No
	Autonomous college of UGC	Yes		√	No
	Regulatory Agency approved Institution (eg. AICTE, BCI, MCI, PCI, NCI)	Yes		-	No
26.	Type of Institution	Co-education	Men	-	Women
		Urban	√	Rural	Tribal
27.	Financial Status	Grant-in-aid	UGC 2(f)	√	UGC 12B
28.	Grant-in-aid + Self Financing	-	Totally Self-financing		-
29.	Type of Faculty/Programme				
	Arts			√	
	Science			√	
	Home Science			√	
	Commerce			√	
	Law			-	
	Computer Science			√	
	P.Ed. (Physical Edu)			-	
	Tech. Edu.			-	
	Engineering			-	

Health Science	-
Management	-
Others (Specify)	-
Degree	M.Phil. in History, Economic, Sociology
Diploma Courses	Post Graduate Diploma in Hospital Services Management,
Certificate Courses	Post Graduate Diploma in Computer Applications Botany, Physics and Home Science
30. Name of the Affiliating University (for the Colleges)	Barkatullah University Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh
31. Special status conferred by Central/ State Government	UGC/CSIR/DST/DBT/ICMR etc.
32. Autonomy by State/Central Govt. / University	State <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Central <input type="checkbox"/> University <input type="checkbox"/>
33. University with Potential for Excellence	UGC-CPE <input type="checkbox"/>
34. DST Star Scheme	-
35. UGC-Special Assistance Programme	DST-FIST <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
36. UGC-Innovative PG programmes	-
1. UGC-COP Programmes	-
2. IQAC Composition and Activities	
2.1 No. of Teachers	11
2.2 No. of Administrative/ Technical Staff	01
2.3 No. of Students	01
2.4 No. of Management Representatives	02
2.5 No. of Alumni	01
2.6 No. of any other stakeholder and community representatives	-
2.7 No. of Employers/ Industrialists	01
2.8 No. of other External Experts	01
2.9 Total No. of members	18
2.10 No. of IQAC meetings held	06
2.11 No. of meetings with various stakeholders	Faculty 02 Students 06
Non-Teaching Staff	Alumni 01 Others 01

2.12	Has IQAC received any funding from UGC during the year? If yes, mention the amount	Yes	√	No	-
		3 Lakhs for XII Plan Period			

2.13 Seminars and Conferences (only quality related)

(i)	No. of Seminars/Conferences/ Workshops/Symposia organized by the IQAC	
	Total Nos.	-
	International	-
	National	-
	State	-
	Institution Level	01
(ii)	Themes	One week training program on ' Quality Sustenance and Faculty Development '.

2.14	Significant Activities and contributions made by IQAC.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IQAC prepared an action plan for 2015-2016 on the basis of feedback received from various stakeholders. • Organised one-week training programme on quality sustenance and faculty development. • Every Saturday, one hour is dedicated to mission cleanliness by teachers and students. • Publication of online journal "e-anveshan' is continued in 2015-2016. • More emphasis was laid on use of ICT: CCE I was based on PowerPoint Presentations, research surveys, reports of field visits and excursions.
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2.15	Plan of Action by IQAC/Outcome	The plan of action chalked out by the IQAC in the beginning of the year towards quality enhancement and the outcome achieved by the end of the year *
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Plan of Action	Achievements
Curriculum Enhancement	Subject curriculum was updated and enhanced through board of studies of the respective department
Extension of built up area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A covered parking lot for staff has been constructed • Extension of auditorium is in progress
Seminar, workshop and training programme	One week training program was organised on Quality Sustenance and Faculty Development
Eco-friendly environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paperless CCE I based on ICT • Campus declared as no-polythene zone

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Conservation of energy by replacing bulbs and tubes by LED and solar lights
Research Promotion	A merit cum financial grant of Rs.5000/- for meritorious research scholar of the college
Emphasis on ICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use of smart classes for multimedia activities such as PowerPoint presentations, internet surfing etc• A three-day computer training for the staff
Installation of bio-metric systems	Three bio-metric systems have been installed to ensure the punctuality of the staff

Criterion - I

Curricular Aspects

1.1 Details about Academic Programmes

Level of the Programme	Number of existing Programmes	Number of programmes added during the year	Number of self-financing programmes	Number of value added / Career Oriented programmes
Ph.D.	19	-	-	-
PG	17	-	04	-
UG	04 + 02	-	04	-
PG Diploma	02	-	02	-
Advanced Diploma	-	-	-	-
Diploma	-	-	-	-
Certificate	03	-	03	-
M. Phil.	03	-	03	-
Total	50	-	16	-
Interdisciplinary			03	
Innovative			-	

1.2 (i) Flexibility of the Curriculum: CBCS/Core/Elective/Open options

The institution offers a wide choice of UG courses for students. Students can make choice of subjects among :

B.A.	47 Group combinations
B.Sc.	07 Group combinations
B.H.Sc.	03 Group combinations
B.Com.	03 Group combinations
B.C.A.	01 Group combinations

Job Oriented Project Work (JOPW) for UG Semester VI and PG Sem I, II, III and IV is compulsory.

Certificate courses with Choice Based Credit System (CBCS) in :
Vermicomposting
Marketing & Processing of Medicinal Plants.

(ii) Pattern of Programmes

Pattern	No. of Programmes
Semester	01 + 04 UG, 16 PG + 03 M.Phil. + 01 BCA Total = 25
Trimester	Nil
Annual	01 B. Lib. & I. Sc. & 01 M. Lib. & I. Sc. Total = 02

1.3 Feedback from stakeholders*

(On all aspects) *Please provide an analysis of the feedback in the Annexure

Alumni	√	Parents	√	Employer	√	Students	√
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Mode of feedback

Online	-	Manual	√	Co-operating schools (for PEI)	-
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1.4 Whether there is any revision/ update of regulation of syllabi, if yes, mention their salient aspects.

Yes, the review and updation of syllabi is done every year through board of studies in all subjects. Reshuffling and 10% of enhancement has been done in English, Botany and Economics etc.

1.5 Any new Department/Centre introduced during the year. If yes, give details

Nil

Criterion - II**Teaching, Learning and Evaluation**

2.1 Total No. of Permanent Faculty

Total	Assistant Professors	Associate Professors	Professors	Others
100	85	Nil	15	Nil

2.2 No. of permanent faculty with Ph D

92

2.3 **No. of Faculty Positions Recruited (R) and Vacant (V) during the year**

Assistant Professors		Associate Professors		Professors		Others		Total	
R	V	R	V	R	V	R	V	R	V
0	10	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	10

2.4 No. of Guest and Visiting faculty and Temporary faculty

Guests faculty

26

Temporary faculty

08

2.5 Faculty participation in conferences and symposia:

No. of Faculty	International level	National level	State level
Attended Seminars/ Workshops	25	66	14
Presented papers	11	40	06
Resource Persons	01	10	05

2.6 Innovative processes adopted by the institution in Teaching and Learning:

- More emphasis on student centric learning through group-discussions, brainstorming, enacting plays and role plays.
- Satellite communication (SATCOM) to teach students through You-Tube, who at times fail to attend classes,
- Students are provided with open educational resources such as Del Net, Inf-Lib Net and N List.
- Students are taken for field visits, excursions, industrial visits etc. to get first hand information.
- Use of smart classes for multi-media activities such as PowerPoint presentations, internet surfing, online excess to e-journals, display of films and documentations.

2.7 Total No. of actual teaching days during this academic year

182

2.8	Examination/ Evaluation Reforms initiated by the Institution <i>(for example: Open Book Examination, Bar Coding, Double Valuation, Photocopy, Online Multiple Choice Questions)</i>	Online multiple questions in CCE
2.9	No. of faculty members involved in curriculum restructuring/revision/ syllabus development as member of Board of Studies/ Faculty/ Curriculum Development Workshop	All faculty members
2.10	Average percentage of attendance of students	75.8%
2.11	Course/Programme wise distribution of pass percentage :	Enclosed Annexure - I
2.12	How does IQAC contribute/ monitor/ evaluate the Teaching & Learning processes	<p>The Institute monitors the teaching quality on the following parameters through feedback from students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject knowledge • Rapport with students • Regularity • Discipline • Teaching skills • Language and expression • Use of ICT • Innovation in teaching methods <p>The resulting impact on students' performance is gauged through internal assessment. The teachers are directed to make their self-assessment and curative measures are taken wherever necessary.</p>
2.13	Initiatives undertaken towards faculty development	

Faculty / Staff Development Programmes	Number of faculty benefitted
HRD programmes	88
Orientation programmes	-
Faculty exchange programme	02
Staff training conducted by the university	09
Staff training conducted by other institutions	19
Summer / Winter schools, Workshops, etc.	14
Others	10

2.14 Details of Administrative and Technical staff			
Category	Number of Permanent Employees	Number of Vacant Positions	Number of permanent positions filled during the Year

Administrative Staff	22 (03 [#] + 08 [§] + 11*)	-	-
Technical Staff	28 (14 [§] + 14*)	02	-

Class I,II*Class III*Class IV

Criterion – III

Research, Consultancy & Extension

3.1 Initiatives of the IQAC in Sensitizing/Promoting Research Climate in the institution

- IQAC has organized a research oriented one week training program on '**Quality Sustenance and Faculty Development**'.
- A merit cum financial grant of Rs. 5000 for outstanding research scholar.
- Continuance of publication of an in-house research journal, e-anveshan.
- Motivate teachers to publish papers in reputed peer reviewed journals

3.2 Details regarding Major Projects

	Completed	Ongoing	Sanctioned
Number	01	02	
Outlay in Rs. Lakh	5,00,000	15,38,000	

3.3 Details regarding Minor Projects

	Completed	Ongoing	Sanctioned	Submitted for funding
Number	03	03		
Outlay in Rs. Lakhs	3,95,000	4,70,000		

3.4 Details on Research Publications

	International	National	Others
Peer Review Journals	36	37	05
Non-Peer Review Journals	04	32	-
e-Journals	03	27	01
Conference proceedings	17	19	-

3.5 Details on Impact factor of publications

Range	Average	h-index	Nos. in SCOPUS
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3.6 Research funds sanctioned and received from various funding agencies, industry and other organisations

Nature of the Project	Duration Year	Name of the Funding Agency	Total Grant sanctioned	Total Grant Received
Major projects	2015-17	UGC Rajya Shiksha Kendra	15,38,000	8,59,000
Minor Projects	2015-17	UGC Rajya Shiksha Kendra		
Interdisciplinary Projects				

Industry sponsored				
Projects sponsored by the University/ College				
Students research projects (other than compulsory by the University)				
Any other (Specify)				
Total				

3.7 No. of Books Published

i) With ISBN No	01	14
ii) Chapters in Edited Books Without ISBN No.		

3.8 No. of University Departments receiving funds from UGC-SAP

CAS	DST-FIST
DPE	DBT Scheme/funds

3.9 For colleges Autonomy CPE DBT Star Scheme

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3.10 Revenue generated through consultancy

Nil

3.11 No. of conferences organized by the Institution

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Level	Inter national	National	State	University	College
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Number	-		-	-	01
Sponsoring agencies					

3.12 No. of faculty served as experts, chairpersons or resource persons

19

3.13 No. of collaboration

International	01	National	02	Any other	03
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3.14 No. of linkages created during this year

17

3.15 Total budget for Research for current year in lakhs
From Funding agency
from Management of University/College

The amount received from projects as well as research fellowships is property utilized.

Total	-
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3.16 No. of patents received this year

Type of Patent	Number
National	Applied
	Granted
	-
	-

International	Applied	-
	Granted	-
Commercialised	Applied	
	Granted	

3.17 No. of Research Awards/ Recognitions received by Faculty and Research Fellows of the Institute in the year

Total	International	National	State	University	District	College
09	01+ 3	01	01+01=2			02

3.18 No. of faculty from the Institution who are Ph. D. Guides and students registered under them

Ph. D. Guides	38
Students registered under them	98

3.19 No. of Ph.D. awarded by Faculty from the Institution

	49
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3.20 No. of Research Scholars receiving the Fellowships (Newly enrolled + existing ones)

JRF	06	SRF	-	Project Fellows	-	Any other	04
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3.21 No. of students Participated in NSS events

University level	64	State level	08	National level	04	International level	-
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3.22 No. of students participated in NCC events

University level	-	State level	100	National level	17	International level	-
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3.23 No. of Awards won in NSS

University level	-	State level	-	National level	-	International level	-
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3.24 No. of Awards won in NCC

University level	-	State level	08	National level		International level	-
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3.25 No. of Extension activities organized

University forum	-	College forum	59	NCC	05	NSS		Any other	46
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3.26 Major Activities during the year in the sphere of extension activities and Institutional Social Responsibility
Extension activities executed by N.C.C.

One day Orientation Programme was organized for UG & PG Freshers.

- Plantation
- Awareness about Traffic Rules
- Lecture on Leprosy

Extension activities performed by N.S.S.

- AIDS awareness
- Blood donation
- Celebration of Yoga Day.
- Rally on World Population Day.
- Shramdan
- One week camp in village Sukhi Sevania.

Activities carried out by the Academic Departments

- Botanical Association was formed.
- Visit was organized to naturopathy centre and Arogya dham Kendra by Botany department.
- Chemistry department signed an MOUs with Scan Laboratories and Jawaharlal Nehru Cancer Hospital.
- Distribution of old clothes in slums by Chemistry department.
- Two research scholars of Chemistry department bagged best paper awards in National Seminar.
- A number of teachers of the College participated in 'Run Bhopal Run' -a health and sanitary drive launched by the district administration
- English department organized workshops on Functional English and Women in Literature.
- A host of faculty members delivered lectures for SATCOM (virtual classes) at RCVP Norohna Academy.
- The students of Geography department visited 'Shastakhedi' to make villagers aware of hygiene and cleanliness.
- A poster exhibition was organized by History department. Students visited to Manav Sangrahalaya and State Museum.
- 52 students of Music department took part in Sitar recital at Delhi under the auspices of WCF and claimed for the Guinness World Records.
- A Professor of the Music department has been felicitated by the Prime Minister for recitation of 'Ram Charit Manas'.
- Students of the Political Science department organized Mock Parliament.
- The students of Psychology department visited Anand Dham (Old Age Home), Arushi (an institute for visually challenged kids) Garima – (a female unit of 1250 hospital) and Mother Teresa Orphanage.

Departmental Highlights

- A number of guest lectures were organized for career assistance by the department of Economics.
- Field visits to Bhimbetika and Delawari.
- Department of Physics prepared a Laboratory Manual.
- Physics department organized a three days training programme on Environmental Management in EPCO.

Criterion – IV**Infrastructure and Learning Resources**

Facilities	Existing	Newly created	Source of Fund	Total
Campus area	06 Acres	-		06 Acres
Class Rooms				56
Laboratories				38
Seminar Halls				07
No. of important equipments purchased (\geq 1.0 lakh) during the current year				
Value of the equipment purchased during the year (Rs. in Lakhs)				
Others				
Faculty Rooms	28			28
Common Room	01			01
Toilets	14			14
Technical Staff Room	10			10
NSS	01			01
NCC	01			01
Departmental Libraries*	08			08
Sick Room	01			01
Storing spaces	05			05
UGC Cell	01			01
WSC	01			01
HEPSN	01			01
SC/ST/OBC/Minority Cell	01			01
Dance Deptt.	01			01

*Some of the teaching departments are maintaining the departmental libraries in their Faculty room.

4.2 Computerization of Administration and Library Administration

Library

Administration and Library are fully computerized.

- Online admission of students.
- Record of Daily Attendance of faculty and the other staff.
- Database of salary of the teaching as well as non-teaching staff.
- Database of academic and other responsibilities.
- Automated through software (SOUL 2.0).
- Bar coded membership cards for all stake holders.
- All titles are bar coded.
- OPAC facility (online Public Access).
- Internet facility (leased line).
- Library campus Wi-Fi enabled.
- e-Resources : Through institutional membership of DELNET.

Delnet Databases

An N-LIST user can access the following database:

Union Catalogue of Books-CCE	12,891,696
Union List of current Periodicals	33,944
Union Catalogue of Periodicals	20,235
Database of Periodical Articles	922,042
CD-ROM Database	22,234
Union List of Video Recordings	6,000
Union List of sound recordings	1,025

4.3 Library services

	Existing		Newly added		Total	
	No.	Value	No.	Value	No.	Value
Text Books						
Reference Books						
e-Books			97000 +1613 (Delnet) 97000 (N-List)			
Journals	65	20	85			
e-Journals			20			
Digital Database						
CD & Video		359 CD 60 VCD 12 VC (Video cassette)				
Others (specify)						

4.4 Technology Up gradation (overall)

	Total Computers	Computer Labs	Internet	Browsing Center	Computer Centres	Office	Departments	Other
Existing	147	01	2 Wi-Fi 4 mbps	01	01	01	24	
Added	-	02		-	-	-	-	
Total	147	03	02	01	01	01	24	

4.5 Computer, Internet access, training to teachers, students and any other programme for technology up gradation (Networking, e-Governance etc.)

- A three day training cum workshop for Lab Technicians
- A paper Computer awareness is made mandatory for B.A. VI semester students

4.6 Amount spent on maintenance in lakhs

ICT

91,000.00

Campus Infrastructure, facilities	1,35,211.00
Equipments	10,240.00
Others	
Total	

Criterion – V

Student Support and Progression

5.1 Contribution of IQAC in enhancing awareness on Student Support Service

- Information regarding all committees: Tutor Guardian, Career Guidance & Counselling, Anti-ragging, Sexual Harassment, Scholarships, HEPSN and special scheme are available on website.
- All Important information are displayed on various notice boards.
- Feedback is taken from students twice a year.
- Students are familiarized with the college through orientation programme.
- Redressed issues are conveyed to the students through 'Samvad Setu' during tutor guardian meeting.

5.2 Efforts made by the institution for tracking the progression

- The departments collect data on students learning outcomes.
- The subject teacher analyses it and takes curative measures.
- Remedial classes are arranged for slow learners.
- Extra coaching and study material is provided to economically weaker students.

(b) No. of students from the state

(c) No. of international students

Men

Women

Demand ratio

Dropout %

UG- Nil, PG- Nil, Ph. D.- Nil, Others -Nil

-

-

-

-

Number 3879

Percentage 100%

Last Year 2013-14

General	SC	ST	OBC	Physically Challenged	Total
1812	649	233	1062	18	3497

This Year 2014-15

General	SC	ST	OBC	Physically Challenged	Total
1663	744	294	1157	21	3879

5.4 Details of student support mechanism for coaching of competitive examinations (if any)

- Identification of students.
- Classification on the basis of their needs
- Syllabus is divided into number of classes

- Lectures are arranged accordingly.

No. of students beneficiaries

-

5.5 No. of students qualified in these examinations

NET	SET/SLET	GATE	CAT	IAS/IPS etc	State PSC	Others
2	-	-	-	-	-	-

5.6 Details of student counselling and career guidance

- Career Guidance and Counseling Cell provided information on career opportunities & vacancies available in prospective sectors and organized Campus Interviews.
- Under Swami Vivekanand Career Margdarshan Yojana (SVCMY), the Training & Placement Cell and the Career Guidance & Entrepreneurship Cell of this college provided guidance and assistance to the students.

Objectives

- To offer training to make them better suited for employment
- To hone skills to cater technical requirements.
- To mold students to meet the corporate expectations and place them in reputed companies based on the expected job profiles.
- To encourage skill development and self employment.

Activities

- Personality Development
- Career Counselling
- Mock interviews
- Seminars
- Placement

Dates	Title and contents	Number of benefited students
21.08.2015 15.09.2015	Training for Campus recruitment: Communication skills, Formal dressing, Group discussion, Mock Interviews, CV making, SWOT Aptitude, Reasoning, Data interpretation, Mathematical aptitude.	170
11.01.2016 04.02.2016	Fashion illustration and designing	69

Date	Companies	Package	No of Students
31.05.2015	Academic Associates	3.00 lacs PA	05
21.09.2015	Om Software	1.20 lacs PA	03
21.09.2015	Om Software optimization	1.20 lacs PA	04
23.09.2015	IFBI for ICICI	2.33 lacs PA	11
26.09.2015	IBM Concentix		19
19.01.2016	ICICI Prudent Life		26
29.01.2016	Infosys		51
30.01.2016	TCS		59
No. of students benefitted			178

5.7 Details of campus placement

On campus		Off campus	
Number of Organizations Visited	Number of Students Participated	Number of Students Placed	Number of Students Placed
08		178	-

5.8 Details of gender sensitization programmes

Project on Eve – Teasing.
Project on Domestic violence
Internet addiction

5.9 Students Activities

5.9.1 No. of students participated in Sports, Games and other events

State/ University level	27	National level	05	International level	01
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No. of students participated in cultural events

State/ University level		National level		International level	
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5.9.2 No. of medals /awards won by students in Sports, Games and other events

Sports :

State/ University level	05	National level	03 Gold	International level	01
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Cultural :

State/ University level	7 Events 18 Students	National level	-	International level	-
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5.10 Scholarships and Financial Support

Number of Students

Amount

Financial support from institution	-	-
Financial support from government	-	-
Financial support from other sources	-	-
Number of students who received International/ National recognitions	-	-

5.11 Student organised / initiatives – College level –Fashion- | Textile

Fairs :

State/University level	-	National level	-	International level	-
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Exhibition:

State/University level	-	National level	-	International level	-
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5.12 No. of social initiatives undertaken by the students

Visit to Old Age Home
Visit to Arushi

5.13 Major grievances of students (if any) redressed: in 14-15

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Criterion – VI

6 Governance, Leadership and Management

6.1 State the Vision and Mission of the institution	<p>Vision - Creating new paradigms of progressive, inclusive and ethical education.</p> <p>Mission - To empower young women with multi skill education and prepare them for responsible and dynamic role in society.</p>
6.2 Does the Institution have a Management Information System	<p>Yes, the College has Management Information System through department of Higher Education Govt. of Madhya Pradesh.</p>
6.3 Quality improvement strategies adopted by the institution for each of the following:	
6.3.1 Curriculum Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Board of Studies, in each subject reviewed the curriculum for its efficacy and appropriateness by enhancing and reshuffling the course content.
6.3.2 Teaching and Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The teachers have focused more on participative learning through project, script writing, book reviews, group discussions and surveys. • Students are given experience of work situations through field visits, excursions, Job Oriented training and industrial visits. • More emphasis was laid on ICT assisted learning.
6.3.3 Examination and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non - traditional CCE I was made entirely based on presentations through ICT. • To maintain transparency in evaluation system, the students were given a privilege to view their answer books of the semester examination on demand.
6.3.4 Research and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Del Net, Inf-Lib Net and N - list facilities were made available. • A forum, 'Knowledge Sharing Club' was developed to deliberate over new advances and prospects in interdisciplinary research. • The faculty was motivated to publish their research papers in peer reviewed journals with high global impact factor. • For quality research, incentives were declared in the form of merit scholarship for outstanding research scholar.

<p>6.3.5 Library, ICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Library is made fully automated library. • Facilities of Del Net Inf-Lib Net, N-list etc. were made available to students as well as teachers. • Latest books were purchased to grow competence and to keep students update with recent developments. • To promote ICT, high speed land line has been procured from Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited (BSNL). • All programmes were given specific time slot to make optimal use of smart classes.
<p>Physical infrastructure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A covered parking place for 50 cars has been added to infrastructure. • Extension of auditorium is in progress. The funds are made available from Janbhagidari Samiti and university Grants Commission.
<p>Instrumentation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many departments have acquired instruments and permanent articles to strengthen their laboratories.
<p>6.3.6 Human Resource Management</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faculty positions were filled through guest faculty in self financing courses. • Human Resource Development was ensured through training cum workshop for teaching and administrative staff. • Due care was taken to assign the administrative job and responsibilities to commensurate with the calibre of individual.
<p>6.3.7 Faculty and Staff recruitment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruitment of Permanent faculty as well as office staff is done by Public Service Commission on behalf of Government of Madhya Pradesh. • Recruitment of Guest faculty is done on contractual basis by an approved committee as per requirement.
<p>6.3.8 Industry Interaction / Collaboration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students were sent to industries, NGOs, Commercial organisations and Scientific laboratories for Job Oriented Project Work and <i>in situ</i> training. • The college has entered into tie up with companies to provide ample job opportunities.
<p>6.3.9 Admission of Students</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online admission through the portal of MP Higher Education, following the reservation

		policy of the state.			
6.4	Welfare schemes for Teaching & Non-teaching Staff	<p>There are number of welfare schemes available for teaching and non-teaching staff. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Provident Fund (GPF) • Contributory Provident Fund (CPF) • Family Benefit Fund (FBF) • Group Insurance Scheme (GIS) • Medical Reimbursement • Free medical check up & treatment in govt. hospitals • Pension/Family pension • Death cum Retirement Gratuity • Housing Loan at a discounted rate of interest • Festival Advance • Grain Advance • All types of leaves and vacations including maternity, paternity, study and duty leave. • Commutation of Pension • Leave encashment • Ex-gratia <p>During the last 4 years, all the staff members (teaching and non-teaching) have contributed to and availed of the benefits of such schemes.</p>			
	Students	Nil			
6.5	Total corpus fund generated	Income from Autonomous	64,35,010.00		
		Janbhagidari	72, 93,457.00		
		ATM Rent	72,000.00		
6.6	Whether annual financial audit has been done	Yes	√	No	
6.7	Whether Academic and Administrative Audit (AAA) have been done?				
		Audit Type	Yes/No	External Agency	Yes/No
		Academic	√	UGC / Commissioner, HE	√
		Administrative	√	UGC Review Team	
		Financial		A.G.M.P Gwalior / Treasury / C.A.	
6.8	Do the University/ Autonomous College declare results within 30 days?				
	For UG Programmes	Yes	√	No	-
	For PG Programmes	Yes	√	No	-
6.9	What efforts are made by the University/ Autonomous College for Examination Reforms?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pattern of question paper are designed to make the assessment of knowledge, skill, 			

	application and power of expression.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer books are displayed to the students on demand.
6.10	What efforts are made by the University to promote autonomy in the affiliated/constituent colleges?
	The university provides all necessary support to college.
6.11	Activities and support from the Alumni Association
	One day cultural (programme) was organized
6.12	Activities and support from the Parent - Teacher Association
	Parents were invited to render their honest feedback on infrastructure, teaching, learning and support services.
6.13	Development programmes for support staff
	A 3 days computer training program was organized for support staff.
6.14	Initiatives taken by the institution to make the campus eco-friendly
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paperless CCE I, based on ICT. • Replacement of bulbs and tubes by LED and solar lights. • Ban on polythene in the campus. • One hour (per week) is dedicated to mission cleanliness. • Extension activities such as propagation of environmental awareness and hygiene among villages in general and women folk in particular during field visits.

Criterion – VII

7. Innovations and Best Practices

7.1 Innovations introduced during this academic year which have created a positive impact on the functioning of the institution. Give details.

- Students centric approaches in teaching-learning, more & more access to internet and computer technology has been promoted in teaching learning.
- Assessment on class room teaching and self-acquired learning through differential mode of evaluation has been adopted.
- Vocational experience to the final year students of graduation and post graduation is provided to have a knowhow of essential qualifications, desirable skills, knowledge, practical training and experience of gainful employment in the related area.

7.2 Provide the Action Taken Report (ATR) based on the plan of action decided upon at the beginning of the year

- A covered parking lot for 50 cars has been constructed.
- Extension of auditorium is in progress
- One week training programme was held on Quality Sustenance and Faculty Development.
- Paperless CCE I, fully based on ICT.
- Polythene free campus.
- Conservation of energy by replacing bulbs & tubes by LED and solar lights
- A merit cum financial grant of Rs.5000 for meritorious research scholar of the college.
- Use of smart classes with multimedia activities such as PowerPoint presentations, internet surfing etc.
- Three bio-metric systems have been installed to ensure the punctuality of the staff.

**Provide the details in annexure (annexure need to be numbered as i, ii,iii)*

7.3 Give two best practices of the institution (Pl. See the format in the NAAC Self-Study Manuals)

BEST PRATICE - 1

Title of the Practice

New Approaches in Teaching, Learning & Evaluation

Objectives of the Practice

- Integration of ICT and modern practices in daily classroom teaching.
- Alternative teaching methodologies to make

the classroom interactions more participative.

- Dissemination of traditional knowledge and scholastic supplements to advanced learners.
- Holistic development by inculcating interpersonal skills and making the students financially independent.

The Context

- The institution has an amalgamation of students from different socio-economic backgrounds endowed with different levels of cognitive abilities.
- It is difficult to impart knowledge to all in the same manner. Therefore, it was necessary to search alternative methodologies of teaching learning & evaluation.

The Practice

- Using diverse methods of teaching - learning and classroom interactions increase the acceptance of knowledge and enhances an intrinsic urge for better performance on the part of the student.
- The better performance in turn boosts the self-confidence level in the student.
- This initiates motivation/ quest for higher & higher benchmarks.

Evidence of Success

- Students are much more sincere and regular in classrooms as compared to the past few years.
- A consistently high pass percentage has been observed during past few years.
- There is a visible change in self-confidence levels of the students and they have been able to translate their knowledge into grateful employment.

Problems Encountered and Resources Required

- It is challenging to make parity between the subject and the teaching-learning approaches as all modes of are not equally pertinent for each subject.
- Owing to time-constraints, at times, it becomes infeasible to provide additional aliquot of knowledge in the classroom.

The resources required are

- Better ICT facilities.
- A rich library with e-books.
- Smart classrooms with teaching aids like LCD, OHP, Visualiser etc. are required for applying different methods of teaching-learning.

BEST PRACTICE – 2

Title of the Practice

Vocational Experience

Objectives of the Practice

- To acquaint the learners with prospects and avenues related to the subject/ program of the study, available in the market.
- To have a know-how of the essential qualifications, desirable skills and knowledge, practical training and experience, if any, of gainful employment in the related area.
- To provide an opportunity to experience the work culture, challenges and threats prevailing in the prospective vocation.

To enable the students to adapt themselves as per the vocational needs or to design an enterprise of their own choice.

The Context

- They hardly got a chance to prepare job-oriented report or present the same amidst peers, guide and experts.
- The College did not have any ready resources for the student to acclimatize her to obtain exposure, to interact with institutional workers and to get a holistic view of the job in question.

The Practice

- Student has to select a job-related project work in any one of her opted subjects.
- A teacher in the department guides the students about various job related areas.
- The students has to indicate her choice in any two vocations one for 1st semester and another for the second semester. Then they compare between the two vocations and finally resort on one vocation after detailed survey.
- The student has to report to the particular Office/ Institute and has to work there for at

least 50 hours.

- Student has to submit the report before commencement of semester examination. Then a viva-voce is conducted in which external experts are invited.
- Every student has to earn at least 40% marks as an eligibility to pass in the final examination.

The College has detailed guidelines for vocational experience.

Evidence of Success

- They get ample opportunities to identify their strengths & weaknesses; get a chance to conquer the challenges; and to tap the opportunities.
- This scheme provides a chance to compare two options, one in first semester and another in second semester. It gives an opportunity to assess and finally decide one as career.
- The vocational experience scheme has helped the students to make up their mindsets and armour themselves for their prospective careers. This scheme has evaded their doubts and resulted in designing a specific road map for a promising career.

As a result, there has been a marked escalation in the number of students getting placements or entering into an enterprise.

Problems Encountered and Resources Required

- The students are offered exposure in some broadly categorized fields only; like teaching, establishing pathology laboratory, banking, advertising, sales & marketing, counselling, insurance etc.
- Many of the organizations have their own activities and exigencies rendering it difficult to accommodate our students in the predetermined time-slot.
- In some circumstances, maintenance of efficacy of work becomes challenging to the student and the teacher as well.

The required resources are:

To have a tie-up with those laboratories/ institutions which have rich facilities, provide hands-on-training, demonstration & practicum and exposure

		to routine functioning.	
7.4	Contribution to environmental awareness / protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental awareness program by students during field visits. • Distribution of alum and fine cloth to filter water among villages. • Nukkad Natak and rally by students of Eco-club. 	
7.5	Whether environmental audit was conducted?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7.6	Any other relevant information the institution wishes to add. (For example SWOT Analysis) Plans of institution for next year	<p>During zero classes, students are oriented and asked for SWOC analysis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Departments of Zoology, Psychology and Geography have to toil hard to get their post - graduate courses back. • Library science department has proposed M Phil. And PGDLN programme for next session. • As per the suggestion of U.G.C. Review Committee for Extension of Autonomy, Centre for Research & Development, will be established. 	

AQAR

2015-16

PART - II

Chairperson	:	Dr. Vandana Agnihotri Principal
Coordinator	:	Dr. H.K. Garg Professor of Zoology
Asstt. Coordinator	:	Dr. Veena Dani Professor of Psychology
Members	{	Dr. G.P. Yadav Dr. Kiran Sharma Dr. Kusum Mathur

INTERNAL QUALITY ASSURANCE CELL
SAROJINI NAIDU GOVERNMENT GIRLS POST GRADUATE AUTONOMOUS COLLEGE
SHIVAJI NAGAR BHOPAL

Annual Quality Assurance Report

Sarojini Naidu Government Girls Post Graduate (Autonomous) College, popularly known as Nutan College, with a brilliant record of 45 years, has been an exemplar of creativity and quality sustenance. Owing to its excellence in curricular, co-curricular and extra-curricular activities, the College stands tall among equals. Acclaimed as one of the best institutes of the state, the College fetched autonomy by UGC and Government of M.P. in 1995-96. Since then, it has made a phenomenal progress in all academic and allied pursuits.

Objectives of IQAC

The tenets customized by the Internal Quality Assurance Cell, as decided during One Week Training Program on 'Quality Sustenance & Faculty Development' 2015-16, are as follows :

- Construction of bench marks through conscious, catalytic & consistent efforts.
- Enhancement in the academic & administrative performance of the institution.
- Promotion of Quality Circle (through Conferences, Webinars, Workshops).
- Creation of learner-centric environment.
- Adoption of interactive & participatory teaching - learning methods.
- Preference to innovative & entrepreneurial approaches.
- Amalgamation of competent learning & skills.
- Inculcation of value system.
- Orientation of faculty towards more & more use of IT.
- Consolidation of management information system (MIS).
- Promotion of interdisciplinary research.
- Networking in neighborhood.
- Linkages & collaborations with equals & others.
- Institutionalization of best practices.

- Recognition as a harbinger of change.
- Development of a strong feedback mechanism from all stakeholders (Students, Parents, Hostellers, Alumni, Society, Employer, Teachers of eminence, etc.)

Composition of IQAC

To sustain the quality initiatives taken by the IQAC in the preceding years ; to bring about further progression in the administrative & academic set up of the College ;and to undertake the exercise of Institutional Assessment & Accreditation, a new Internal Quality Assurance Cell has been constituted w.e.f. July 04, 2016 :

1.	Dr. Vandana Agnihotri	Chairperson
2.	Dr. H.K. Garg	Coordinator
3.	Dr. Veena Dani	Member
4.	Dr. G.P. Yadav	Member
5.	Dr. Kiran Sharma	Member
6.	Dr. Kusum Mathur	Member

Policy & Role of IQAC

The Quality Assurance Cell prepares a trajectory for all departments, office and working committees to attain the institutional goals and objectives. The Cell emphasizes on institutionalization of quality parameters while providing adequate flexibility to fit into their specific requirements. The Cell :

- Stimulates the academic departments to supplement, enrich or redesign the existing curriculum (in congruence with the institutional mission and vision) to accommodate the incipient global, national and local occupational requirements;
- Prompts all schools of studies to introduce additional enrichment programs with possible flexibility in time frame ; horizontal as well as vertical kinesis ;
- Introduces different methods of teaching-learning; together with instrumentation, practicum, hands-on training, excursions or field visit, whenever applicable.
- Emphasizes participative learning, innovation and research ;
- Ensures optimal use of ICT during class room interactions;
- Monitors regular follow up of Academic Calendar;
- Proposes a variety of examination patterns (for internal assessment) like group discussion, seminar, quiz, power point presentation, assignments & projects based on surveys, innovations or research, to choose from ;

- Encourages the departments to develop synergistic relationship or collaborations with industries & other institutes;
- Persuades adequate use of library resources and regular footfall in the central reading room; and
- Transparency in method of evaluation.

Besides laying its focus on curriculum, teaching learning evaluation, research and infrastructure, the Cell also attempts to create a conducive and barrier-free environment by institutionalizing a few initiatives :

- On line admissions;
- e-library membership for all;
- Inception of knowledge sharing club, Red Ribbon club, Reading club, Eco club, Anti-Cancer club, Mental Health club and Nutan Band;
- Concept of wall magazine, book of the week, thought for the day, go-green campus drive ;
- Celebration of Nutrition week, World Ozone day, Science day, Human Rights day, Mental Health Awareness day, Environment day, Bhopal gas tragedy Anniversary;
- Organization of career fare, free eye check-up, blood check-up and blood donation camps; and
- Restriction of polythene, use of mobile etc.
- These practices are initially delegated to a particular department and later on institutionalized.

Meetings organized by IQAC Team

During the session 2015-16, meetings were held once in every two months. Records are maintained and action plan decided accordingly.

Date	Time	Venue	Itinerary	Number of Participant
Jul 16, 2015	3:00 pm	Principal Chamber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Extension of time period for submission of SSR ✓ Preparation of SSR with fresh compilation ✓ Institutional website to be linked with NIC. 	11

Sep 04, 2015	12:30 pm	Principal's Office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Blue print of quality initiatives, maintenance and augmentation for the academic session 2015-16 ✓ Road map for the next 10 years - VISION 2025 ✓ CCE-I to be based on Innovations, Surveys & Small Investigations. 	12
Oct 08, 2015	12:00 pm	Principal Chamber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Present status of groundwork for Self Study Report to be sent to NAAC ✓ Propose plan for strengthening of IQAC in the College from the grants received from UGC ✓ Estimation and budget provisions in view of the impending visit of the NAAC Peer Team. 	11
Nov 04, 2015	12:30 pm	Conference Room	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Preparation of proposal and plan to organize One Week Research Oriented Faculty Recharge Training cum Workshop ✓ Mobilization of Funds from participating faculty. 	07
Jan 13, 2016	2:30 pm	Conference Room	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Progress, review and determination of deadline for Self-Study Report ✓ Report of the One Week Training Program on Quality Sustenance & Faculty Development to be prepared ✓ Analysis to made from the feedback obtained ✓ Formation of feedback formats and procurement of feedback from all the stakeholders. 	06
Mar 21, 2016	3:00 pm	Conference Room	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Progress of Preparation of Self Study Report ✓ Printing of SSR ✓ Executive Summary ✓ Feedback analysis and Report writing ✓ AQAR 2015-16 ✓ Procurement of Affiliation Certificate from University ✓ Updation of College website ✓ IQAC Road map for 2016-17 	06

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING

First Meeting

Principal Chamber : Thursday, the 16th July 2015 (03:00 PM).

- In view of the fact that 1/3rd of the faculty and half of the office staff have been shifted elsewhere. In place, nearly equal number of teachers and employees has joined the College, hence the data needs to be compiled afresh.

- A request letter may be sent to CAPU, NAAC to seek an extension up to April 30, 2016.
- The re-accreditation work should commence with immediate effect so that report writing could finish by April 30, 2016.
- The information, relating to the Academic Year 2014-15 must also be taken into account while preparing the final report.
- The number of pages in the final SSR should be restricted up to 200, as far as possible.
- All vital statistics must be collected and compiled as on July 31, 2015 to avoid inconsistency in data.
- Before the completion of SSR, the College would upload the institutional data for 'All India Survey in Higher Education' on MHRD website as a pre-requisite to the submission of SSR.
- Also, the ICT Committee of the College would be asked to link the newly constructed institutional website with NIC.
- To keep clarity and ensure accountability at the time of validation of report by the Peer Team of NAAC, the academic attainments of the ex-faculty members be supplanted by that of the new ones.

Second Meeting

Principal's Office : Friday, the 04thSep 2015 (12:30 PM).

- All the decision taken in the last meeting were read by the Coordinator and approved by the Chairperson and Members.
- A brief follow-up, of the decisions taken in the last meeting, was presented.
- The Chair reiterated that the academic attainments of the ex-faculty members must be supplanted by that of the new ones. And all relevant data must be procured and compiled as on July 31, 2015 to avoid any discrepancy.
- The Member Coordinator informed the Chair that necessary information has been sought from all Academic Units (Departments running Post Graduate, Under Graduate & Diploma Courses) and Activity Cells, in specific formats, each one customized as per the needs of an individual Cell or the Department.
- The Heads of all departments assured to return the duly filled formats on or before Sep 12, 2015. They also promised to complete their Departmental Profiles by Sep 18, 2015.

- The Coordinator presented a blue-print of Quality Initiatives, Maintenance and Enhancement for the academic session 2015-16. Accordingly, the Non-Traditional Examination, being undertaken as CCE-I, shall be entirely based on Innovations, Surveys, Small bits of Research & ICT. The contents would only be accepted by the faculty, in soft copies and the presentations be made through MS Power Point.
- In order to sensitize the students to make judicial use of natural resources, the faculty would be asked NOT to accept any hard copy in Non-Traditional Modes of Examinations. As evidence, the soft copies may be preserved in semester-wise folders on the desktop.
- The departments should lay emphasis on Innovative and Participative Teaching Learning Techniques and give more prominence to Learner-centric approaches.
- The IQAC took this opportunity to concoct a Road Map for next 10 years, which assumes to :
 - ✓ Computerize each department of the College in terms of Faculty Profile, Academic, Administrative and Financial Pursuits.
 - ✓ Make all official correspondence with regard to Leave, Claims and Attendance of the Staff On-line (except in case of those memos which require official signatures).
 - ✓ Afford On-line CCE Examinations and Instant Results.
 - ✓ Record Student's Attendance through Biometric devices.
 - ✓ Propagate all Notices & Information through SMS, e-mails and College Portal.
 - ✓ Deliver Notes, Question Papers and Laboratory Manuals on College Portal.
 - ✓ Have preference for Webinars over Seminars, Conferences and Presentations as the latter entail vast expenditure on transportation, hospitality and on-site arrangements.
 - ✓ Fix Policy, Time limit and Desired Outcome for every day-to-day Academic and Administrative Quest.
 - ✓ Commence New Vocational Courses after ascertaining their global prospects and contemporary relevance.
 - ✓ Introduce Choice Based Credit System, bring Interdisciplinary Courses together and encourage Interdisciplinary Research.

Third Meeting

Principal Chamber : Thursday, the 08thOct 2015 (12:00 PM).

- All the minutes of the previous meeting were read by the Member Coordinator and approved by the Chair and the Members.
- A brief follow-up, of the decisions taken in the last meeting, was presented.
- The Internal Quality Assurance Cell has received a sum of Rs. 300,000.00 from University Grants Commission for establishment and consolidation of IQAC. As per the Statement of Income & Expenditure submitted by the former IQAC convener, an amount of Rs. 102,195.00 has been utilized during 2012-15 and the balance amount of Rs. 197,805.00 is left in the IQAC account.
- Of the total allocation, 15% (Rs. 45,000.00) has to be earmarked for SC and 7.5% (22,500.00) for ST. The left-over sum of Rs. 232,500.00 shall be disbursed in General.
- It is hereby decided to update the Internal Quality Assurance Cell with a new Printer, Scanner, Hard Disk and an Internet Data Modem with USB Card. The amount payable on the above items shall be deducted under the head 'Office Equipment & ICT Communication Expenses'.
- Dr. Kusum Mathur would be the Professor-in-Charge of IQAC Accounts and Mr. LN Chandhani (Office Accountant) would provide secretarial assistance.
- Mrs. Deepanjali Shukla would help in maintaining the files, data and records of the IQAC as well as NAAC.
- The Accountant, the Office Assistant and the Attendant shall be paid a maximum of Rs. 4,000.00; 6,000.00 and 2,000.00 per annum respectively, on the basis of actual work done by them. These expenses would be deductible under the head, 'Hiring Charges for Secretarial & Technical Services'. However, if any of them fails to discharge his/her responsibilities on time, no payment shall be made to him/her. In such cases, the services would be hired from outside and payment to the outside agency shall be made accordingly.
- All other disbursements, from IQAC Accounts, shall be made as per existing practice.
- Keeping in view, the forthcoming visit of NAAC Peer Team, it seems worthwhile to make financial provisions for Laboratory Apparatus, Books, Computers, Restoration, Renovations, Transportation, Lodging-Boarding, Hospitality of the Peer Team and other eventualities. The Office would seek information from the Departments & Cells and make budgetary provisions accordingly.

Fourth Meeting

Conference Room : Wednesday, the 04thNov 2015(12:30 PM).

- All the decision taken in the last meeting were read by the Coordinator and approved by the Chairperson and Members.
- In order to ensure pre-accreditation quality sustenance and to develop a system for conscious, consistent & catalytic improvement in the academic and administrative set up to the College, it has been decided to organize a Research Oriented Faculty Recharge Programme during the pre-semester examination gap.
- The training programme would last for one week commencing from Nov 16, 2015 till Nov 21, 2015.
- The theme of the training program shall be, '**Quality Sustenance & Faculty Development**'.
- The programme will comprise invited talks, group discussions and open discourse on Zero budget enterprises, Value additions, Institutional Social Responsibilities, Green Campus Initiatives and so on.
- Eminent Academicians, Former Principals, Administrators, Financial Experts and Peers would be invited to speak on Quality Concept, Choice Based Credit System, Academic Performance Enhancement, Time & Personal Management, Quality Sustenance in Teaching, Learning, Evaluation & Research, Prevailing Purchase Rules etc.
- All the expenses, expected to be incurred on the programme, shall be equally borne by the participants and no financial assistance will be sought from the College. Most of the faculty members & HODs have voiced their readiness to participate and contribute for the programme on self-finance basis.

Fifth Meeting

Conference Room : Wednesday, the 13th Jan 2016 (02:30 PM).

- All the decision taken in the last meeting were read by the Coordinator and approved by the Chairperson and Members.
- The Coordinator informed the Chair that Self Study Report (SSR) writing is on full swing since the last week of November 2015.
- There are seven criteria in SSR, which have been allotted to following committee members :

Criterion - 1	:	Dr. G.P. Yadav
Criterion - 2	:	Dr. Ruchira Choudhary

Criterion - 3	:	Dr. Kiran Sharma
Criterion - 4	:	Dr. Indira Javed
Criterion - 5	:	Dr. Mamta Maheshwari & Dr. Pratishtha Khare
Criterion - 6	:	Dr. Kusum Mathur
Criterion - 7	:	Dr. Shikha Shrivastava & Dr. Rohit Trivedi

- Four criteria have already been submitted and the remaining three would be finished by the end of this month.
- An internal committee is formed to monitor and assist in preparing the first draft. This committee will also review the work done by the members. The committee comprises:

Review (1-4)	:	Dr. Veena Dani
Review (5-7)	:	Dr. Bharti Jain

- On the basis of the first draft and the data compiled by the committee members, the final draft shall be prepared by **Prof. H.K. Garg**, Coordinator and **Prof. Veena Dani**, Assistant Coordinator, IQAC. The final draft shall be made available to all constituents of the College to point out hyperboles, omissions or typological errors that may creep in while compilation, editing or printing. Thereafter, it will not be feasible to entertain any claim in this regard.
- It is reiterated that feedback forms have to be constructed afresh, for all the stakeholders, viz :
 - ✓ Faculty Feedback on Principal
 - ✓ Students' Feedback on Faculty
 - ✓ Students' Feedback on College
 - ✓ Hostellers' Feedback
 - ✓ Alumni' Feedback
 - ✓ Parents' Feedback

Dr. H.K. Garg and Dr. Veena Dani will construct the Feedback Forms anew.

Sixth Meeting

Conference Room : Monday, the 21stMar 2016 (03:00 PM).

- All the decisions taken in the last meeting were reported by the Coordinator and approved by the Chair and Members.

- The Coordinator informed the Chair and Members that SSR writing is on the verge of completion.
- The Coordinator is working on Executive Summary and the SSR will be ready for printing in a day or two. The IQAC Members, once again, restated that all constituents of the College must go through the entire SSR before its printing so that ambiguities, inaccuracies or typographical errors, if any, that might have appeared at the time of compilation, editing or formatting, can be corrected. A notice, to this effect, shall be placed on the Notice Board.
- Having deliberated on various pros and cons, the Committee Members have agreed upon to assign the printing task to a Government press like *Madhyam*.
- As discussed during the first meeting dated July 16, 2016 the validity of LOI has been expired in Nov 2015. Therefore, a fresh LOI has to be submitted by the first week of May or as and when the SSR print is ready (whichever is earlier). In view of the fact, affiliations need to be procured from the parent University for all the courses conducted by the College. The Coordinator reiterated that affiliation in desired format is a pre-requisite for acceptance of LOI.
- The Principal has been requested to entrust the responsibility of website updation on regular basis to a senior faculty. Links for Academic Time Table, Annual Calendar, Self-Study Report (NAAC), IQAC, Student Support System, etc. need to be created.
- Information has to be procured from different academic departments and activity committees for preparation of AQAR 2015-16. The IQAC has prepared a tailored format to furnish the details of activities and achievements pertaining to the year 2015-16.
- Feedbacks obtained from various stakeholders have to be analyzed and transcribed into graphical representations.

Quality Initiatives taken by IQAC

This year, the Internal Quality Assurance Cell has taken certain initiatives :

- The College has developed a plan for next one decade in the name of **VISION 2025** ;
- ICT has been made an integral component of teaching - learning. All the academic departments have been allotted time-slots to organize lectures in smart classes ;
- The internet facility has been strengthened and fortified with Wireless Fidelity ;

- Teachers have been motivated to make use of satellite communication for teaching -learning.
- During zero classes (at the onset of new session), lectures & discussions on personality development, communication skills, soft skills, interview, SWOC analysis were held.
- Traditional teaching-learning methods have been increasingly supplemented with other approaches like, innovation, research, surveys, mock-drills, role plays, enactments, group discussion, demonstration, quiz, charts and models.
- The students have been progressively familiarized with real state of affairs through Job Oriented Projects. New avenues are being explored.
- To promote learning by observation & participation, *in-situ* visits like excursions, study tours, industrial & corporate visits have been organized.
- To maintain the standard of research and to make the research work more innovative, interdisciplinary and productive, the role of 'Research Monitoring Committee' has been redefined.
- The process of evaluation has been made more transparent by displaying the valued answer books to the students, after declaration of results ;
- The academic departments have entered into collaboration and signed the memorandum of understanding with other equivalents ;
- Consultancy has been initiated and community linked extension activities were given precedence.
- The Career Guidance & Placement Cell has extended its functional dominion. As a result an unprecedented number of students were selected for jobs, during the year.
- Feedback from students on teachers has been restructured and from teachers on principal has been introduced for the first time ;
- Physical infrastructure have been augmented, which included extension of auditorium, individual car parking slots, toilets etc. ;
- Biometric machines have been installed to ensure timely presence of faculty and office staff.
- All official correspondence, with the Department of Higher Education, executed through Management Information System.
- Facility for online learning resources like, Del-Net, Inf-Lib-Net, & N-List has been extended to all students and faculty members.

- Financial transparency, initiated by IQAC, was followed by every department.
- The College principal extended her timings to listen to the problems of faculty members and students.
- As a measure of road safety, wearing a helmet, while driving a two-wheeler, was made mandatory to one and all.
- Students were made aware of fuel conservation, by ensuring time-to-time overhauling of vehicles, turning off engines at signals etc., through orientation programs conducted by traffic police.

ANALYSIS ON THE BASIS OF FEEDBACK

Assessment of Principal as Leader of the Institution

1. Administrative capability

2. Decision making

3. To promote academic work

4. Interest in Co-curricular activities

5. Work delegation among colleagues

6. Problem solving capability

7. Impartiality

8. Straightforwardness

9. Availability

10. Crisis management capacity

11. Implementation of Government policies & programs

12. Ability to utilize the potential of subordinates

13. Praise for excellent work

14. To upgrade the institution's image in the field of higher education

15. Personality traits

16. As a Role Model

17. Ability of planning & implementation

18. Ability to evaluate the capacity of subordinate after receiving feedback

19. Resource mobilization

The Principal is the torch bearer and the motivator for faculty and students. Consequently, it becomes imperative to have a genuine feedback of the faculty on the functioning of the principal. It's a reflection of the 'good' characteristics of the Chair and suggests areas for further improvement.

During the year 2015-16, a new feedback form was constructed. It involves 18 parameters along with the comments on a few desirable personality traits: honesty, diligence, passion, benevolence, punctuality and transparency. Every parameter was assessed on a four point scale : excellent, very good, good and average. In order to maintain the candor of feedback; directives were given to NOT to reveal their own identity by putting name or signature. A detailed analysis of the faculty response on principal is enumerated hereunder:

- **Administrative Capacity**

The highest response was 'very good' (50%), followed by 'good' (21%) and 'average' (14%).

- **Decision Making**

The modal reaction was 'very good' (44%), followed by 'good' (26%). A few faculty members expressed the decision making ability of the Principal as 'excellent' (19%).

- **To Promote Academic Work**

There was mixed response on this point. Thirty percent faculty members gave their response on 'excellent' whereas, 28% gave on 'average'.

- **Interest in Co-curricular Activities**

Promoting curricular activities lead to overall development of the students. It is apparent from the obtained data that highest percentage was recorded for 'excellent' (35%), followed by 'very good' (30%)

- **Work Delegation Among Colleagues**

This parameter indicates one of the essential managerial qualities of the head of the institution. Analysis of responses revealed that highest number of responses were given to 'excellent' (44%) followed by 'very good' (26%).

- **Problem Solving Capability**

There are many unforeseen problems which occur during day-to-day functioning of the College. The faculty members look up to the principal to seek solutions to these problems. Majority of faculty rated the Principal as 'very good' followed by 'good' (23%) and 'excellent' (21%).

- **Impartiality**

This is a highly crucial trait which brings harmony amongst the employees. The maximum number of responses were obtained for 'excellent' (37%), 'very good' (30%) and 'good' (21%).

- **Straight-forwardness**

There was a peak on 'excellent' (42%), followed by 'very good' (26%) and 'good' (23%).

- **Availability**

The above mentioned parameter is of utmost importance for the smooth functioning of the institution. The faculty members rated the principal as 'very good' with 40% of the responses, followed by 'excellent' (28%).

- **Crisis Management Capacity:**

Responses recorded on this parameter were highest for 'very good' (53%), followed by 'good' (19%). A mixed response was also observed as equal number of faculty responded for 'excellent' and 'average' (14% each).

- **Implementation of Government Policies and Programs**

The analyzed responses revealed a progressive curve, as the least response (7%) was recorded for average, 16% for 'good', 33% for 'very good' and 44% for 'excellent'.

- **Ability to Utilize the Potential of Subordinates**

A splintered mandate was received for 'excellent' and 'very good' (35 % each), followed by 'good' (16%).

- **Praise for Excellent Work**

The faculty' appraisal on this parameter was the highest for 'very good' (35%), closely followed by 'excellent' (33%).

- **To Upgrade the Institution's Image in the Field of Higher Education**

Majority of faculty considered her 'very good' (33%) or 'good' (28%) in upgrading the overall image of the Institution among common masses.

- **Personality Traits**

On personality traits like – honesty, diligence, passion, benevolence, punctuality and transparency, the faculty holds a very high opinion. The principal received maximum 'excellent', followed by 'very good' and 'good', on almost every trait.

- **As a Role Model**

The faculty accepts her as a 'very good' (41%) or 'good' (26%) role model for others.

- **Ability of Planning and Implementation**

Majority of the faculty indicated a response for 'very good' (49%), followed by 'excellent' (21%).

- **Ability to Evaluate the Capacity of Subordinates after Receiving Feedback**

For this parameter, a similar trend is perceived as majority opted for 'very good' (49%) and 'excellent', (23%).

- **Resource Mobilization**

Almost a similar trend of response was observed on this issue too. The foremost response was 'very good' (37%) followed by 'excellent' (26%).

By and large, it can be surmised that the faculty's assessment of the Principal as leader of the Institution was on the criteria of 'very good' and 'excellent'.

Students Feedback on College

1.1 Satisfaction with the Choice of Courses available

1.2 Offering tough tasks to Advanced Learners

1.3 Paying extra attention to Weaker Students

2.1.1 Light and Ventilation

3.1 Communication of College Notices

4.1 Sanctity and Transparency in Evaluation

4.2 Use of Non-traditional Methods in Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE)

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

4.3 Timely Declaration of Results

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

5.1 Rating of Reading Room Facility

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

5.2 Do you get the Books (to take home) for sufficient time period?

5.3 Do you get the Photocopy facility in Library?

5.4 Is the behavior of the Library Staff cordial ?

6.1 Practice Sessions for various Sports

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

6.2 Game Equipments

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

6.3 Sports kit and Refreshment

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

7.1 Taste of food

7.2 Cleanliness

7.3 Quality of Service

8.1 Availability and Cleanliness of Drinking Water

8.2 Cleanliness of Class-rooms

9.1 Do you find the college helpful in your personality development?

9.2 Does the College reinforce Extra-curricular talents?

9.3 Do you find the Tutor Guardian Scheme beneficial?

Sincere feedback from stakeholders is a germane indicator of quality realization. It's a regular practice for the IQAC to obtain students' feedback through questionnaire. Students were asked to give their honest response by choosing one of the five alternatives without revealing their identity.

The responses of the students on various parameters have been analyzed as follows :

- **Satisfaction with the choice of course available**

The highest numbers of responses from the students of all the three faculties were 'good' followed by 'very good' and 'excellent'.

- **Offering tough tasks to advanced learners**

Though the responses received from the students were almost similar, yet 27% of the students from the faculty of Arts rated it 'excellent' whereas 13% students sought 'improvement'.

- **Paying extra attention to weaker students**

Graphic representation indicates that students were not much satisfied on this parameter; as 23% students of Commerce, 17% of Science and 13% of Arts expressed the need of improvement.

- **Light and ventilation**

By and large, the college comprises clean and tidy infrastructure and therefore, students appeared to have been satisfied about it. Consequently, the overall response was 'good' followed by 'very good'.

- **Communication of Notices & Information**

The students of Science faculty voted 50% for good, 20% for very good and 13% for excellent. The students from Commerce faculty also seemed equally satisfied. However, most of the students from Arts faculty rated this parameter on average and few on very good.

- **Evaluation System**

It is evident from the obtained data that students had faith in the sanctity and transparency of evaluation. On an average, 40% of the students from all the three faculties had scaled fairness and transparency as 'good', 20% as 'excellent' and 20% as 'very good'. Only 3% felt that this system needs improvement. For using non-traditional methods in Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation, the students' feedback ranged from 'good' to 'very good'. When the students were asked to give their opinion on timely declaration of results, the highest percentage of response was for excellent (34%) followed by very good (29%) and good (25%).

- **Library**

- a) **Reading - room facility**

The highest number of replies from the students fell in the category 'good' followed by 'average'. There is much room for improvement in this area.

- b) **The issuing time period for a book** got maximum responses as 'good' followed by 'excellent'.

- c) The students from Commerce and Arts faculties were mostly satisfied with the **photocopy facility** extended by the library. However, the students from Science faculty had a fractured mandate. Almost parallel opinions were received on the behavior of library staff.

- **Sports**

The feedback was taken on the following points :

- ✓ Practice sessions
- ✓ Game equipments
- ✓ Sports-kit and refreshments

For all the three major points of concern, the majority of the responses vacillated between 'good' and 'very good'. However, 18±1% of the students expressed that game equipments, sports-kit and refreshments need improvement.

- **Canteen**

On an average, the students were satisfied with the services of the canteen, the taste of the food, hygiene and rated them as 'good' and 'very good'.

- **Cleanliness**

Responses of students were taken on two aspects:

- Availability & purity of drinking water, and
- Sanitation inside the class rooms

On both the aspects, the modal values oscillated around 'good' and 'very good'.

- **Student Progression**

Inquiries were made as :

- ✓ Do you find the college helpful?
- ✓ Does the college reinforce extra-curricular talent?
- ✓ Do you find the guardian tutor scheme beneficial?

80% students responded 'yes' on the first inquiry, 87% 'yes' on the second and 83% 'yes' on the third one.

Students Feedback on Faculty

1. Teacher as a Motivator for learning

2. Discipline in Classroom

3. In Offering Help to Students

4. In Providing Solution to Problems

5. Teacher as a Role Model

6. In Updating Subject Knowledge

7. Use of IT in Teaching

8. To Develop Life Skills

9. Supportive in Personality Development

10. To Reinforce Noble Deeds

11. To Develop Sense of Social Responsibility

12. To Propagate Values

Students' feedback on faculty has a great bearing as it marks the areas on which faculty need to focus and improve. During the session 2015-16, the feedback was taken on 12 aspects, which are recorded as follows:

- **Teacher as motivator for learning**

The students from Arts faculty regarded teachers as an 'excellent' (67%) or 'very good' (20%) motivator for learning. 63% students from Science faculty rated them to be 'very good' and 17% as 'excellent'. In Commerce faculty, 40% students found them 'good' whereas 20% 'very good'.

- **Discipline in classroom**

47% students of Science and the same percentage of learners from Arts assumed to have 'very good' discipline in the class-room, followed by 'excellent'. However, the students of Commerce faculty had diversified responses.

- **Offering help to students**

Arts faculty got maximum responses on 'very good' (44%) and 'excellent'. Science students expressed 27% of the responses on 'very good' and 33% on 'excellent'.

- **Teacher as a role model**

60% of the students from Arts faculty considered their teachers to be 'excellent'. Science and Commerce faculties came later.

- **Update subject knowledge**

Analysis shows that Commerce faculty needs improvement in updating subject knowledge, as 17% students marked on the option, 'needs improvement'.

- **Use of IT in teaching**

Only 29% of all the College students rated for use of IT in teaching-learning as 'good', while 22% believed to be 'very good'. From the upcoming session, faculty needs to be encouraged for increasing use of IT in teaching and learning.

- **In developing life skills**

30% students from Science and Arts faculties considered their teachers to be 'excellent' in developing life skills among learners. However, the students from Commerce faculty counted them to be 'average'.

- **Supportive in Personality development**

Through the opportunities offered by the teaching staff, 37% of the students opined 'excellent', followed by 23% 'very good'. The Science faculty bagged 50% responses on 'very good' and 20% on 'excellent'.

- Reinforcing noble deeds
- Develop sense of social responsibility
- To Propagate Values

The students of Arts rated their faculty as 'excellent' with 50%, 40% and 37% responses on all three points, respectively. Maximum number of responses for the Science faculty were on 'very good' and for the commerce faculty on 'good'.

Feedback on Hostel

The hostel facility plays a crucial role in students' life. It is rightly called a 'Home away from home'; Nutan Girls Hostel offers ample facilities for the hostellers. However, obtaining feedback and working upon the same is our regular practice.

There are eight criteria included in the questionnaire: room, food, cleanliness and entertainment, provision of water, visitors' room, internet facility and staying with local guardians.

On the first criteria, opinion was obtained on two aspects lighting and ventilation. The analysis revealed that approximately 78% of the responses were given on 'adequate'.

- Food: The quality of food is rated average with little variation.
- Cleanliness of toilets 'needs improvement' (66%) and cleanliness of common room clinched with 71%.
- Entertainment facility: By and large, majority of the students expressed 'satisfaction' on this parameter. For indoor games, their responses were 'average'. The hostellers have suggested a 'need of improvement' for outdoor games.
- Provision of water: For drinking water, the response is 'average'.
- Visitors' room has been rated 'satisfactory'.
- Internet facility 'needs improvement'.
- Permission to stay with local guardians is rated 'satisfactory'.

Alumni Feedback on College

1. Do you feel proud to be associated with this college as an ex-student of this college?

2. How far the knowledge and skills you obtained from this college were beneficial to you for getting a job?

3. What changes do you perceive in this college? Express your views in light of your past experience.

a) College Campus

b) Canteen

c) Class room

d) Student Support

e) College building

f) Library

g) Information Technology

Alumni Association strengthens the bond between the ex-students and the alma mater. It also allows the present students to get in touch with their older counterparts to learn from their experiences.

The Alumni Association of the college, recognized as NOGA (Nutan Old Girls Association) has been functioning for the last 20 years. Though most of the girls have settled far-away with their families, they somehow manage to visit their old institution and provide us a frank opinion for its advancement.

- **Do you feel proud to be associated with this college as an ex-student ?**

The question was responded optimistically by the alumnae. Almost 91% expressed that it is a 'matter of honour' for them to be associated. Remaining 09% also seemed positive as they answered 'yes'.

- **How far the knowledge and skills you obtained from this college were beneficial to you in getting a job?**

There was a mixed response as the ex-students from Commerce and Science stream appeared contented with 74% and 68% respectively, while the one from Arts side seemed to be a little on the fence with 48%.

- **What changes do you perceive in this college? Express your views in light of your past experience?**

There were a few parameters on which the responses were taken. A brief summary of analysis is as follows:

- **College Campus**

- ✓ The College campus looks splendid (may be, because the government organizations are not so maintained).
- ✓ An additional garden Kokila-Kanan adds beauty to the campus.
- ✓ Parking lots for four-wheelers give an organized look.
- ✓ The bust of Sarojini Naidu placed in front of the main gate looks gorgeous.

All the responses were qualitatively analyzed and an overall impression was found to be 'positive', 'average' or 'negative' with 84%, 16% and nil responses respectively.

- **Canteen**

The alumnae, who had studied before 2005, expressed that the College canteen has been metamorphosed over the years, in all respects. Its cleanliness, seating facility, quantity of food and service were 'excellent'.

Other ex-students felt that the quality and service of the food improved significantly. Overall, 89% alumnae rated it 'excellent', 07% 'very good' and 04% 'good'.

- **Classrooms**

The highest percentage of response was gathered for 'good' (52%) followed by 'very good' (28%) and 'average' (20%). The alumni were delighted to see the addition of 'smart class' in the new wing. Having come across state-of-the-art facilities in metros, multinational companies and elsewhere, they insisted upon hi-tech laboratories and sophisticated class-rooms.

- **Student Support Facilities**

Improvement on this front was reported in the feedback. The maximum number of responses were given to 'good' (67%) followed by 'very good' (23%) and 'average' (10%).

- **Library**

There were diverse responses from the alumni, which are enumerated below:

- More space needed (43%).
- Old and torn books should be discarded (67%).
- Reading room facility with enough space must be improvised (52%).
- Library timings should be extended (39%).

- **Information and Technology**

The feedback indicated that majority of the ex-students expressed a dire need to strengthen the IT facility in the college (79%). Merely 21% felt that the college provided enough IT facility.

- **Sports**

- ✓ The indoor and outdoor sports needed definite time slots.
- ✓ Sports facility should be provided during morning and evening hours.
- ✓ Sports events should be organized frequently.

- **How would you like to see your college in 5 years from now?**

There were very interesting responses recorded by the alumni. A few of these are given below:

- ✓ I wish my college to gain name and fame at the national level.
- ✓ I wish to have a separate wing for vocational training.

- ✓ I wish the College to be known for its Skill enhancement.
- ✓ I wish the College to have the status of a Deemed University.

- **What help and suggestions would you offer to make it an 'institute par excellence'?**

To make the Institute-par-Excellence, the alumnae responded as below:

- ✓ Involvement of ex-students in college societies
- ✓ Contribution of funds for specific development plans.
- ✓ Ready to be associated with NSS wing of the college
- ✓ Can inspire students for social obligations and community services
- ✓ Arrange excursions for hostel students.
- ✓ Donate books to needy students.

Parents Feedback on College

1. Getting admission in this college for your ward is a matter of pride for you

2. The admission procedure of the college is fair and accurate

3. Your evaluation regarding the academic activities of the college

4. Facilities available in the college for teaching & learning of the curriculum

5. Use of IT in teaching & Learning

6. Your opinion regarding applicability of the course in day-to-day life

7. Fairness in examination & evaluation pattern

8. Opportunities for all-round personality development of the students

9. Opportunities for extra-curricular activities

10. Efforts to inspire for fulfilling social obligations

The college is committed for all round personality development of the students. In this wake, various efforts are made throughout the academic session. However, evaluation of the institutional efforts by the parents is absolutely necessary as this evaluation paves way towards excellence. A few parameters were included in the parent's feedback format and their responses were collected.

- **Getting admission in the college in this college for your ward is a matter of pride for you**

In response to this 68% parents gave their opinion on 'totally agree', whereas 30% reported as 'agree'.

- **The admission procedure of the college is fair and accurate**

A very large number of parents were 'totally agree' (77%), and 19% 'agree'. Only 4% replied 'undecided'.

- **Evaluation regarding academic activities of the college**

Maximum number of responses were 'excellent' (46%), followed by 'very good' (38%) and 'good' (10%). Only 6% responses were 'average' and none suggested for improvement.

- **Facilities for teaching learning**

The highest percentage (47%) of response was given for 'agree', 21% for 'totally agree', 9% on 'good' and 13% on 'average'.

- **Use of IT in teaching and learning**

56% gave their response as 'good', 15% on 'very good' and 13% 'on excellent'.

- **Applicability of the course in day to day life**

44% responded 'good'.

- **Fairness in examination and evaluation pattern**

The parents expressed their response as excellent (43%).

- **Opportunities for all round personality development**

The highest response was 'very good' (37%) followed by 'average', 'good', and 'excellent' with 21%, 20% and 18% respectively.

- **Opportunities offered for extracurricular activities**

The parent's response was 'very good' (31%) followed by 'good' (28%) and 'excellent' (22%).

It is the obligatory for college to propagate and inspire the feeling of social responsibility. The efforts of the college were acknowledged by the parents as 'very good' (37%), 'good' (24%) and 'excellent' (15%).

One Week Training Programme on
Quality Sustenance & Faculty Development
November 16-21, 2015

Internal Quality Assurance Cell

Sarojini Naidu Government Girls Post Graduate Autonomous College, Bhopal

Coordinator's Address :

Higher Education has witnessed turbulent changes over the past few decades. On one side is the mushrooming of colleges at every nook of the city, churning out unfinished graduates, on the other side, there has been a steady decline in the educational standards, where academics and values, both seem to have taken a back seat.

The reason is quite simple, though nobody ever likes to accept. The collegiate education system is amazingly stringent and inimical to change. Firstly, the academic decisions are taken at the political level and slapped on the educational guild. Secondly, the over-enthusiastic administration is always in a hurry to implement the same at once, without sensitizing the academic executors and stakeholders. To this, quality initiatives are never roused from within the system ; when introduced from outside, they are resisted ; if imposed, they are ritualized. Therefore, most of the initiatives succumb at the very embryonic stage.

On a globe, where ICT offers all advanced tools like teleconferencing, e-mail, audio-learning, satellite classes, interactive voice response system, webinars etc., to the budding scientists, engineers and administrators, our undergraduates are still relying on hard copies of notes or exam ready booklets for easy scores.

The IQAC strongly felt an urgent need of active involvement of teachers, learners and the society to deliberate over the quality issues with due sensitivity and insight. With this ideology, the Quality Assurance Cell has organized a one week capacity building program on Quality Sustenance and Faculty Development. The program comprised a series of invited guest lectures, group discussions and brain storming sessions on academic, administrative, intellectual, financial, personal, time and stress management. A brief itinerary of the programme is given hereunder :

Itinerary		
Day - 1	2015/11/16	
INAUGURATION	Value Education Vs Quality Education	A Quest for Excellence
Coordinator's Address Dr. H.K Garg	Shri S.C. Behar Former Chief Secretary Govt. of M.P.	Dr. H.K. Garg Director, IQAC Coordinator, Steering Committee
Principal's Speech Dr. Vandana Agnihotri		

Day - 2		2015/11/17	
Quality Culture in HE : Concept & Assessment	Alzheimer's : A Disease of 21 st Century	Inclusive Education	
Dr. Pramila Maini Former Director, IEHE Ex-Member, EC NAAC	Dr. Veena Dani Professor of Psychology	Mrs. Kala Mohan Educational Management Consultant & Child Counselor	
Day - 3		2015/11/18	
Quality Challenges & Sustenance	Store Purchase Rules, 2015	Striving for Excellence	
Dr. Shashi Rai Member, State HE Council Ex-Member UGC, NAAC	Mrs. Veena Bhanupriya Former Additional Director Dept. of Finance, M.P.	Mr. I.S. Dani Former Addl. Chief Secretary, M.P. Chairman, Land Reforms	
Day - 4		2015/11/19	
Quest for Peace & Happiness	RUN BHOPAL RUN (A Health & Sanitary Awareness Event involving 10,000 natives)		
Mr. Rajesh Jagesiya Trainer cum Facilitator The Art of Living, Bengaluru	Collector Bhopal District, Bhopal		
Day - 5		2015/11/20	
Balanced Diet In Indian Context	Self Appraisal for PBAS & CAS	Green Research : Prospects & Perspectives	
Mrs. Amita Singh Expert, Nutrition & Dietetics	Dr. Bharti Jain Professor of Chemistry	Dr. Moni Mathur Retired Professor of Botany	
Day - 6		2015/11/21	
Making Money with Joy	Investment : Pros & Cons	VALEDICTORY	
Mr. Pradeep Karambelkar Investment Advisor	Mr. L.D. Pandit Ex Manager M.P. Coop Bank	IQAC Team	

Feedback on IQAC Training Programme

1. To what extent was the training material incorporated as per your expectations?

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

2. Did you find the training modules to be useful in academic pursuits?

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

3. To what extent were you acquainted training material incorporated as per your expectations?

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

4. How much did you gather on the topics discussed during the training programme?

■ Excellent
 ■ Very Good
 ■ Good
 ■ Average
 ■ Needs Improvement

5. The quality/standard of training

■ Too much
 ■ Sufficient
 ■ Less

6. Time earmarked for each lectures/session

■ Too much
 ■ Sufficient
 ■ Less

7. To what extent did you gain proficiency by this training?

■ Too much
 ■ Sufficient
 ■ Less

8. Did you find audio-visuals effective in understanding the training material?

■ Too much
 ■ Sufficient
 ■ Less

The IQAC organized One Week Training Programme on **Faculty Department & Quality Enhancement** from Nov 16 to Nov 21, 2015. The efforts made by the entire IQAC team resulted into a grand success. At the completion of the workshop, feedback was obtained from the participants / faculty members.

The format contained 8 parameters. The details are enumerated below:

- **To what extent was the training material incorporated as per your expectations?**

In response to this question, 67% faculty members opted for 'very good' followed by 'excellent' (29%) and 'good' (5%).

- **Did you find the training modules to be useful in academic pursuits?**

The relevance of the course was a vital parameter in the present context as the target audience comprised veteran minds and elite academicians. The obtained

responses revealed a highest peak (67%) on 'very good', trailed by 13% on 'excellent' and 17% on 'good'.

- **To what extent were you acquainted with the training material incorporated in the lectures?**

Since, the IQAC made it a point to include only those topics which were innovative, directly relevant and instrumental in boosting up the thought process of the faculty members, it was apparent to reclaim 31% responses on excellent, 65% on 'very good' and 02% each on 'good' and 'average'.

- **How much did you gather on the topics discussed during the training programme?**

As a learning outcome, this question was asked to assess the amount of learning that took place during the discourse. The feedback clearly indicated that the highest responses were received for 'very good' (55%), followed by 'excellent' (11%) and 'good' (10%).

- **The quality/ standard of training**

As regards the standard of the training, a highly encouraging response was obtained with 97% 'very good'. The overwhelming response was indicative of the fact that the selection of speakers and the strategies adopted by the organizing committee for quality control proved to be apt and fruitful.

- **Time earmarked for each lecture /session**

More of less similar responses were obtained for this parameter too, with highest response of 97% for 'adequate/ suitable'.

- **To what extent did you gain proficiency by this training?**

60% of the faculty member gained sufficient proficiency while others put on still higher than their expectation.

- **Did you find audio–visuals effective in understanding the training material?**

Regarding efficacy of audio-visual aids, majority of participants found them either 'very good' (38%), 'good' (35%) or 'excellent' (34%).

The awe-inspiring feedback received from the faculty members pointed towards the grand success of the venture. The enthused faculty put forth the following remarks :

- The programme was conducted in clock-work fashion. Every minute was meticulously utilized.
- The Coordination of the team and execution of the program was excellent. Very well organized.
- The subject matter and level of lectures was excellent.

- Topics were picked from various fields. Selection of topics was good.
- Highly comprehensive information was propagated.
- The training was highly productive.
- Very high level of subject matter, stimulated the faculty for further learning.
- The issues taken up were pertinent with day-to-day pursuits. The workshop was well-planned and offered solutions to the problems encountered in daily chores.
- Best resource persons were called. Their lectures were practically relevant.
- The theme for every lecture was very helpful in professional and personal life.
- The workshop was very informative. This will prove to be beneficial for personal and institutional growth.

At the same time, the faculty offered certain futuristic suggestions :

- The duration for question answer session should be more.
- A training programme on IT should be arranged.
- Videos or visuals of working environment from best institutions can be shown.
- One useful lecture may be arranged every fortnight.
- A copy of all the lectures should be provided.
- A workshop on teaching, learning and evaluation may also be arranged.
- This type of training programmes should be arranged twice a year.
- International issues should also be incorporated in future programs.
- Involvement of participants should be increased.
- More time to be allotted for discussion between resource person and faculty members.

Faculty Feedback on Principal
(Assessment of Principal as Leader of the Institution)

	Excellent उत्कृष्ट	Very Good बहुत अच्छा	Good अच्छा	Average औसत	Needs Improvement सुधार आवश्यक
1- Administrative capability प्रशासकीय क्षमता					
2- Decision Making निर्णय लेने की क्षमता					
3- To promote academic work अकादमिक कार्यों को बढ़ावा देना					
4- Interest in co-curricular activities सह-पाठ्येत्तर गतिविधियों में रुचि लेना।					
5- Work delegation among colleagues. सहकर्मियों से काम ले सकना					
6- Problem solving capability समस्या समाधान की क्षमता।					
7- Impartiality सबके साथ एक-सा व्यवहार					
8- Straight Forwardness स्पष्टवादिता/स्पष्ट रूख					
9- Availability / Accessibility उपलब्धता					
10- Crisis is Management capacity संकटावस्था में प्रबंधन क्षमता					
11- Implementation of Govt. Policies & Programmes शासकीय योजनाओं व कार्यक्रमों का क्रियान्वयन।					
12- Ability to utilize the potential of subordinates अधीनस्थों की क्षमता को विदोहन करने की योग्यता।					
13- Praise for excellent work. उत्कृष्ट कार्य की प्रशंसा करना।					
14- To upgrade the institutions image in the field of higher education उच्च शिक्षा के क्षेत्र में महाविद्यालय की छवि उन्नत करना					
15- As a Role Model आदर्श के रूप में					

16- Ability for future planning & implementation भविष्य की योजना एवं क्रियान्वयन की क्षमता					
17- Ability to evaluate the capacity of subordinates अधीनस्थ की योग्यता का आकलन करने की क्षमता					
18- To take right/fair decision after obtaining feed back फीडबैक प्राप्त करने पर उचित निर्णय लेना					
19- Efforts for resource mobilization संसाधन गतिशीलता के प्रयास					
20- Evaluation of personality characteristics: व्यक्तित्व की विशेषताओं का मूल्यांकन					
i. Honest ईमानदार					
ii. Diligent मेहनती					
iii. Passionate लगनशील					
iv. Kind-hearted सहृदयी					
v. Punctual समयबद्ध,					
vi. Transparency पारदर्शिता					

सरोजिनी नायडू शासकीय कन्या स्नातकोत्तर (स्वशासी) महाविद्यालय शिवाजी नगर, भोपाल
आंतरिक गुणवत्ता आश्वासन प्रकोष्ठ (Internal Quality Assurance Cell)

Student Feedback on College

Session 2015-2016

Class / कक्षा

Subject Offered

चयनित विषय

Please do not reveal your identity. This information will be used only for qualitative improvement of the college infrastructure and teaching. Read each question carefully and express your opinion by putting a (√) mark on any one of the options 1 to 5.

कृपया अपनी पहचान प्रकट न करें। इस जानकारी का उपयोग सिर्फ महाविद्यालय की अधोसंरचना एवम् अध्यापन कार्य में गुणात्मक सुधार हेतु किया जायेगा। प्रत्येक प्रश्न को ध्यान से पढ़िये व अपने मत को 1 से 5 तक किसी एक विकल्प पर (√) लगाकर अंकित करें।

I. Evaluation of Course and Teaching पाठ्यक्रम एवं अध्यापन का मूल्यांकन

Excellent उत्कृष्ट	Very Good बहुत अच्छा	Good अच्छा	Average औसत	Needs Improve' सुधार आवश्यक
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1.1 Satisfaction with the choice of courses available
उपलब्ध पाठ्यक्रम के विकल्पों से संतुष्टी

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1.2 Applicability of the course content in real life situations
पढाये जाने वाले पाठ्यक्रम की वास्तविक जीवन परिस्थितियों में उपादेयता

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1.3 Sufficient Use of Information Technology
सूचना प्रौद्योगिकी का पर्याप्त उपयोग

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1.4 Offering challenging tasks to advance learners
प्रतिभावान छात्राओं को चुनौतीपूर्ण कार्य सौंपना

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1.5 Paying extra attention to weaker students
कमजोर छात्राओं पर अतिरिक्त ध्यान देना

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II. Class room & Infrastructure अध्यापन कक्ष

2.1 Light & ventilation
प्रकाश एवं हवा

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III. Administration and Management of College महाविद्यालय प्रशासन एवं प्रबंधन

3.1 Communication of college notices
महाविद्यालय में सूचना का संप्रेषण

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3.2 Time duration normally taken by the office in solving your fees related, scholarship etc. & other problems
आपकी फीस सम्बन्धी, छात्रवृत्ति आदि व अन्य समस्याओं का समाधान करने में कार्यालय द्वारा लिया जाने वाला समय

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IV. Examination system परीक्षा प्रणाली

	Excellent उत्कृष्ट	Very Good बहुत अच्छा	Good अच्छा	Average औसत	Needs Improve' सुधार आवश्यक
4.1 Pattern of question papers प्रश्नपत्र की पद्धति					
4.2 Fairness & Transparency in evaluation- मूल्यांकन की पारदर्शिता व निष्पक्षता					
4.3 Grading system instead of traditional marking pattern पारंपरिक अंक पद्धति के स्थान पर ग्रेडिंग प्रणाली					
4.4 Use of non-traditional method in Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) सतत् समग्र मूल्यांकन (CCE)में गैर-पारंपरिक विधा का उपयोग					
4.5 Timely execution of examination परीक्षा प्रणाली की समयबद्धता					
4.6 Timely declaration of results परीक्षा परिणाम की समयबद्ध घोषणा					

V. Student Support System छात्र सहायता तंत्र

Library पुस्तकालय

5.1 Taking regular benefit of library facility पुस्तकालय सेवा का निरंतर लाभ लेना					
5.2 Rating of reading room facility वाचनालय की सुविधा का आंकलन					
5.3 Whether the allotted days and time period for issuing books are sufficient? क्या पुस्तकें निर्गमित करने के लिये आवंटित दिन व समयावधि पर्याप्त हैं?	Yes		No		
5.4 Do you get the books (to take home) #for sufficient time period? क्या पुस्तक पढ़ने (घर ले जाने) के लिये निर्धारित समय खंड पर्याप्त है?	Yes		No		
5.5 Do you study the reference book/magazines & journals in the library? क्या आप पुस्तकालय में संदर्भ पुस्तकें/पत्रिकाओं व जर्नल्स का अध्ययन करते हैं?	Yes		No		
5.6. Do you get the photocopy facility in library? क्या पुस्तकालय में फोटो कॉपी सुविधा उपलब्ध है?	Yes		No		
5.7 Do you use the internet & Delnet facility regularly? क्या आप internet एवंDelnetसुविधा का नियमित उपयोग करते हैं?	Yes		No		
5.8 Is the behavior of the library staff cordial? क्या पुस्तकालय के स्टाफ का व्यवहार सौहार्द्रपूर्ण है?	Yes		No		

VI. Sports खेलकूद

Excellent उत्कृष्ट	Very Good बहुत अच्छा	Good अच्छा	Average औसत	Needs Improve ment सुधार आवश्यक
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6.1 Indoor games
अन्तःकक्ष खेल

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6.2 Play ground games
मैदानी खेल

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6.3 Practice sessions for various sports
विभिन्न खेलकूद के अभ्यास सत्र

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6.4 Game equipments
खेल के साधन

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6.5 Sports kit & Refreshment
खेल किट व उपाहार

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VII. Canteen कैटीन

7.1 Taste of food
भोज्य पदार्थ का स्वाद

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7.2 Cleanliness
स्वच्छता

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7.3 Seating Arrangement
बैठक व्यवस्था

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7.4 Availability of snacks
खाद्य पदार्थों की उपलब्धता

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7.5 Quality of Service
सेवा की गुणवत्ता

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VIII. Cleanliness स्वच्छता

8.1 Campus cleanliness
परिसर की स्वच्छता

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8.2 Availability and cleanliness of drinking water
पेय जल की उपलब्धता व स्वच्छता

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8.3 Cleanliness of class rooms
अध्यापन कक्ष की स्वच्छता

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IX. Student Progression छात्र उन्नति

9.1 Do you find the college helpful in your personality development?
क्या महाविद्यालय आपके व्यक्तित्व विकास में सहायक है?

Yes

No

9.2 Does the college develop life skills?
क्या महाविद्यालय जीवन कौशल को विकसित करता है?

Yes

No

9.3 Does the college reinforce extra-curricular talents?
क्या महाविद्यालय में शिक्षणोत्तर प्रतिभा को प्रोत्साहन मिलता है?

Yes

No

- 9.4 Do you participate in NCC/NSS?
क्या आप NCC/NSS के प्रतिभागी हैं? Yes No
- 9.5 Do you find the guardian tutor scheme beneficial?
क्या आप शिक्षक अभिभावक योजना को लाभदायक मानते हैं? Yes No
- 9.6 Do you take benefit of scholarship?
क्या आप छात्रवृत्ति का लाभ लेते हैं? Yes No
- 9.7 What changes would you like to bring in the cultural activities of the college?
महाविद्यालय के सांस्कृतिक कार्यक्रमों में आप क्या बदलाव लाना चाहेंगे?
10. What are the reasons of being absent in the class room?
कक्षा में अनुपस्थित रहने के क्या कारण हैं?

Tick the appropriate answer सही उत्तर पर निशान लगायें

- a. Health problem
स्वास्थ्य समस्या
- b. Not learning anything new in class
कक्षा में कुछ नया सीखने नहीं मिलता
- c. Transportation problem
आवागमन समस्या
- d. Lack of time
समय अभाव
- e. Time of class: too early/too late
कक्षा का समय: जल्दी/देर से होना
- f. Availability of short answers in question bank
प्रश्न बैंक में संक्षिप्त उत्तर की उपलब्धता
- g. Lack of interest
रुचि का अभाव
- h. Preparation of competitive examinations
प्रतियोगी परीक्षा की तैयारी
11. What contribution can you offer to the college on the following points?
निम्न बिंदुओं पर महाविद्यालय के लिये आप क्या योगदान दे सकते हैं?
- a. Instillation of ethics
मूल्यों की स्थापना
- b. Donating Books for poor students
निर्धन छात्रों को पुस्तकें दान देना
- c. Making campus clean & green
महाविद्यालय परिसर को स्वच्छ व हरा रखना
- d. Creating social awareness
सामाजिक जागरूकता निर्मित करना

सरोजिनी नायडू शासकीय कन्या स्नातकोत्तर (स्वशासी) महाविद्यालय, शिवाजी नगर, भोपाल

Students' Feedback on Faculty

This information will be used only for qualitative improvement of the college infrastructure and teaching. Read each of the following questions carefully and express your opinion by putting a tick mark (✓) on the appropriate option.

इस जानकारी का उपयोग सिर्फ महाविद्यालय की अधोसंरचना एवम् अध्यापन कार्य में गुणात्मक सुधार हेतु किया जायेगा। प्रत्येक प्रश्न को ध्यान से पढ़िये व अपने मत को 1 से 5 तक किसी एक संख्या पर (✓) लगाकर अंकित करें।

	Excellent उत्कृष्ट	Very Good बहुत अच्छा	Good अच्छा	Average औसत	Needs Improve सुधार आवश्यक
• Teacher as a Motivator for Learning सीखने के लिये प्रेरक के रूप में					
• Discipline in Classroom कक्षा में अनुशासन					
• Offering Helpto Students छात्राओं को सहायता					
• Providing Solution to Problems समस्या का समाधान देना					
• Teacher as a Role Mode शिक्षक (आदर्श) एक भूमिकाप्रतिमान के रूप में					
• Update Subject Knowledge विषय का अद्यतन ज्ञान					
• Use of IT in Teaching अध्यापन में IT का उपयोग					
• In developing Life Skills जीवन कौशल विकसित करने में					
• Supportive in Personality Development व्यक्तित्व विकास में सहायक					
• Reinforcing Noble deeds अच्छे कार्य को प्रोत्साहन देना					
• To Develop Sense of Social Responsibility सामाजिक दायित्व का बोध विकसित करना					
• To propagate values मूल्यों का संवर्धन करना					

सरोजिनी नायडू शासकीय कन्या स्नातकोत्तर (स्वशासी) महाविद्यालय, शिवाजी नगर, भोपाल
आंतरिक गुणवत्ता आश्वासन प्रकोष्ठ

छात्रावासी छात्राओं के लिए प्रश्नावली (Questionnaire for Hosteller)

Session 2015-16

As you are a resident of the college hostel, your feedback about the hostel arrangements is required. Give your sincere response by choosing any one of the available options, without disclosing your identity. This information will help us in understanding the status of our hostel facilities and to develop it further.

महाविद्यालय छात्रावास के निवासी होने के नाते छात्रावास की व्यवस्था के बारे में आप से कुछ जानकारी पूछी जा रही हैं। अपना नाम गोपनीय रखते हुए, दिये गये विकल्पों में से किसी एक विकल्प को चुनते हुए अपने विचार पूरी ईमानदारी से दीजिये। इस जानकारी का उपयोग छात्रावास के सुविधाओं की वस्तुस्थिति जानने व उसे सर्वर्धित करने के लिए किया जायेगा।

1. Room :

i. How do you find your room? आपका कक्ष कैसा है?	Very comfortable अत्यंत सुविधाजनक	Comfortable सुविधाजनक	Uncomfortable असुविधाजनक
ii. Lighting arrangement in room : कक्ष में प्रकाश व्यवस्था	Very well बहुत अच्छी	Adequate पर्याप्त	Inadequate अपर्याप्त
iii. Ventilation in room : हवा की आवाजाही	Very good बहुत अच्छी	Adequate पर्याप्त	Inadequate अपर्याप्त
iv. Size of room : हवा की आवाजाही	Very good बहुत अच्छी	Adequate पर्याप्त	Inadequate अपर्याप्त

2. Food: भोजन

i. Quality of food : भोजन की गुणवत्ता	Very good बहुत अच्छी	Adequate पर्याप्त	Inadequate अपर्याप्त
ii. Cleanliness of kitchen & food किचन व भोजन की स्वच्छता	Very good बहुत अच्छी	Adequate पर्याप्त	Inadequate अपर्याप्त
iii. Menu for Lunch & Dinner दोपहर एवं रात्रि के भोजन का मेन्यू	Healthy menu with variation each day स्वास्थ्यप्रद मेन्यू व प्रतिदिन बदलाव के साथ	Somewhat healthy with some variation कुछ स्वास्थ्यप्रद व थोड़ा बदलाव	No variation/ everyday same कोई बदलाव नहीं/ एक-जैसा
iv. Change in food as per student's demand छात्रों की माँग के अनुसार भोजन में बदलाव	Always हमेशा	Some time कभी-कभी	Never कभी नहीं

3. Cleanliness: स्वच्छता

i. Classroom :कमरे की	Very Clean अत्यंत स्वच्छ	Clean स्वच्छ	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
ii. Toilets : प्रसाधन कक्ष/शौचालय	Very Clean अत्यंत स्वच्छ	Clean स्वच्छ	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
iii. Campus : परिसर	Very Clean अत्यंत स्वच्छ	Clean स्वच्छ	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
iv. Common Room : सामान्य कक्ष	Very Clean अत्यंत स्वच्छ	Clean स्वच्छ	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक

4. Entertainment Facility : मनोरंजन सुविधा

i. Entertainment : मनोरंजन	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
ii. Indoor Games : अंतः कक्ष खेल	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
iii. Outdoor Games : मैदानी खेल	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
iv. Is there a Provision of reading room in hostel? क्या छात्रावास में अध्ययन हेतु पठन कक्ष की व्यवस्था है?	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक

5. Safety Provision : सुरक्षा व्यवस्था

Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
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6. Provision of Water : पानी की व्यवस्था

i. Drinking Water facility : पीने के पानी की सुविधा	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
ii. Water facility in Toilets: प्रसाधन कक्ष में पानी की सुविधा :	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
7. Availability of news paper, magazine & books in reading room पठन कक्ष में समाचार पत्र इत्यादि पत्रिकाएँ व पठनीय पुस्तकों की उपलब्धता	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
8. Is there a provision of separate room to meet visitors? आगन्तुकों से भेंट करने के लिये अलग कक्ष की व्यवस्था है?	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
9. Rating of Internet facility इन्टरनेट सुविधा का आंकलन	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
10. Distance from hostel to market छात्रावास से मार्केट की दूरी	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
11. Staying arrangement for parents अभिभावकों के ठहरने की व्यवस्था	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक
12. Permission to stay with local guardians स्थानीय संरक्षकों के पास रहने की छूट	Satisfactory संतोषप्रद	Average औसत	Needs improvement सुधार आवश्यक

सरोजिनी नायडू शासकीय कन्या स्नातकोत्तर (स्वशासी) महाविद्यालय, शिवाजी नगर, भोपाल
Alumni' Feedback on College
Session 2015-16

General Information:

सामान्य सूचना:

1. नाम

Name:

2. शैक्षणिक योग्यता

Educational Qualification:

3. महाविद्यालय में प्रवेश का सत्र

Session of admission in the college :

4. महाविद्यालय से अध्ययन समाप्ति का सत्र

Session of end of studying from the college:

5. व्यवसाय

Occupation:

As you are an alumna of this college, your views and suggestions, in this context, are important to us. Kindly express your opinion with regard to the following questions.

इस महाविद्यालय की पूर्व छात्रा होने के नाते महाविद्यालय के संदर्भ में आपके विचार एवं सुझाव हमारे लिये महत्वपूर्ण हैं। कृपया निम्न प्रश्नों के संदर्भ में अपने विचार प्रकट करें।

1.	Do you feel proud to be associated with this college as an ex-student of this college? इस महाविद्यालय के पूर्व सदस्य होने पर क्या आप गर्व अनुभव करते हैं ?	
2.	How far the knowledge and skills you obtained from this college were beneficial to you for getting a job? रोजगार पाने के लिये इस महाविद्यालय से प्राप्त ज्ञान एवं कौशल कहाँ तक लाभदायक थे ?	

3.	<p>What changes do you perceive in this college? Express your views in light of your past experience.</p> <p>आप इस महाविद्यालय में क्या परिवर्तन देखते हैं? पूर्व अनुभव के आलोक में अपना उत्तर दीजिये।</p>	
i.	<p>College Campus</p> <p>महाविद्यालय परिसर</p>	
ii.	<p>Canteen</p> <p>कैंटिन</p>	
iii.	<p>Class room</p> <p>अध्यापन कक्ष</p>	
iv.	<p>Student Support / Facilities</p> <p>छात्र सहायता / सुविधायें</p>	
v.	<p>College Building</p> <p>महाविद्यालय भवन</p>	
vi.	<p>Library</p> <p>पुस्तकालय</p>	
vii.	<p>Information and Technology</p> <p>IT सूचना एवं प्रौद्योगिकी</p>	
viii.	<p>Sports</p> <p>खेलकूद</p>	
4.	<p>How would you like to see your college in 5 years from now ?</p> <p>आज से 5 वर्ष बाद आप अपने महाविद्यालय को कैसा देखना चाहेंगे?</p>	
5.	<p>What help & suggestions would you offer to make it an 'institute par excellence'?</p> <p>इस महाविद्यालय को उत्कृष्ट बनाने के लिये आप क्या सहायता व सुझाव देना चाहेंगे ?</p>	

Parents' Feedback on College
Curriculum, Learning, Infrastructure & Support Services)
2015-16

Respected parents,

It is a matter of pleasure that your ward is studying in this institution. We are committed for her all round personality development. Your evaluation on the efforts made by the institution will steer us towards excellence. Kindly read each of the following questions and record your opinion by putting a tick mark (✓) in the most pertinent box.

हर्ष का विषय है कि आपकी पाल्य हमारी संस्था में अध्ययनरत है। उनके बहुआयामी व्यक्तित्व विकास हेतु हम कृत संकल्पित हैं। इस हेतु संस्था द्वारा किये जा रहे प्रयासों के प्रति आपका मूल्यांकन हमें उत्कृष्टता के लिए दिशा-निर्देशित करेगा। कृपया प्रत्येक प्रश्न को पढ़कर उनके समक्ष दर्शित उपर्युक्त मूल्यांकन खंड में सही का चिन्ह (✓) लगाकर अपना अभिमत अंकित करें।

1. Getting admission in this college for your ward is a matter of pride for you
आपके पाल्य का इस महाविद्यालय में प्रवेश पाना आपके लिए गर्व की बात है—

2. The admission procedure of the college is fair and accurate
महाविद्यालय की प्रवेश प्रक्रिया सही एवं निष्पक्ष है—

3. Your evaluation regarding the academic activities of the college
इस संस्था की शैक्षणिक गतिविधियों के संबंध में आपका मूल्यांकन

4. Facilities available in the college for teaching & learning of the curriculum
पाठ्यक्रम के अध्ययन व अध्यापन हेतु महाविद्यालय में उपलब्ध सुविधाएं

5. Use of IT in teaching & Learning
अध्ययन व अध्यापन में IT का उपयोग

6. Your opinion regarding applicability of the course in day-to-day life
पढाये गये पाठ्यक्रम की उपादेयता के बारे में आपका मूल्यांकन

7. How do you find office of this college in terms of following points
इस महाविद्यालय के कार्यालय को निम्न बिंदुओं पर आप कैसा पाते हैं?

I. Efficiency
कार्य तत्परता

II. Behavior of the employees
कर्मचारियों का व्यवहार

III. Availability of the staff during office hours
कार्यालयीन समय पर उपलब्धता

8. Fairness in examination & evaluation pattern
परीक्षा व मूल्यांकन की निष्पक्षता

9. Library facility in the college
संस्था की पुस्तकालय सुविधा

पूर्णतः सहमत	सहमत	अनिश्चित	असहमत	पूर्णतः असहमत
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